

Supplementary material:

A day-ahead market model for power systems: benchmarking and security implications

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I. ECONOMIC DISPATCH MODEL

The economic dispatch (ED) is a linear model for optimizing the behavior of generating units in the system. We use this model as a base case scenario when comparing the system performance because it is often the basis for the most frequently used market models in the literature. In addition, it is simple for implementation and has a fast solving time.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \min_{P_g, PD_s, PC_s, P_r, D_d} \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{g \in N_G} P_{g,t} \cdot b_g \\
 & + \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{s \in N_S} (PD_{s,t} + PC_{s,t}) \cdot b_s + \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{r \in N_R} P_{r,t} \cdot b_r \\
 & + \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{d \in N_D} (D_{sch,t} - D_{d,t}) \cdot b_{ds} \quad (1a)
 \end{aligned}$$

s.t.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left(\sum_{g \in N_G} P_{g,t}^i + \sum_{r \in N_R} P_{r,t}^i + \sum_{s \in N_S} PD_{s,t}^i - \sum_{s \in N_S} PC_{s,t}^i \right) \\
 & - \sum_{d \in N_D} D_{d,t}^i + \sum_{\substack{f \in N_F \\ i \neq j}} F_{f,t}^{i,j} = 0, \quad \forall t, \forall i, j \in Z \quad (1b)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$P_g^{min} \leq P_{g,t} \leq P_g^{max}, \quad \forall \{g, t\} \quad (1c)$$

$$P_{g,t+1} - P_{g,t} \leq RU_g, \quad \forall \{g, t\} \quad (1d)$$

$$P_{g,t} - P_{g,t-1} \leq RD_g, \quad \forall \{g, t\} \quad (1e)$$

$$PD_s^{min} \leq PD_{s,t} \leq PD_s^{max}, \quad \forall \{s, t\} \quad (1f)$$

$$PC_s^{min} \leq PC_{s,t} \leq PC_s^{max}, \quad \forall \{s, t\} \quad (1g)$$

$$E_s^{min} \leq E_{s,t} \leq E_s^{max}, \quad \forall \{s, t\} \quad (1h)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{s,t} &= (1 - SD_{rate}) \cdot E_{s,t-1} + \eta_{C,s} \cdot PC_{s,t} \\
 & - 1/\eta_{D,s} \cdot PD_{s,t} + SI_{s,t} - SW_{s,t}, \quad \forall \{s, t\} \quad (1i)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$0 \leq SW_{s,t} \leq SW_s^{max}, \quad \forall \{s, t\} \quad (1j)$$

$$E_{s,t=T} \geq E_{s,t=0}, \quad \forall \{s, t\} \quad (1k)$$

$$0 \leq P_{r,t} \leq P_r^{max}, \quad \forall \{r, t\} \quad (1l)$$

$$0 \leq D_{d,t} \leq D_{sch,t}, \quad \forall \{d, t\} \quad (1m)$$

$$0 \leq F_{f,t} \leq F_f^{max}, \quad \forall \{f, t\} \quad (1n)$$

The economic dispatch is formulated as a cost-minimization problem with the objective of minimizing the total costs in the system, subject to technical constraints. The economic dispatch (ED) is a linear model for optimizing the behavior of generating units in the system. We use this model as a base case scenario when comparing the system performance because it is often the basis for the most frequently used market models in the literature. In addition, it is simple for implementation and has a fast solving time. The economic dispatch is formulated as a cost-minimization problem with the objective of minimizing the total costs in the system, subject to technical constraints. The node balance equation (1b) ensures the balance between generation and demand in all control zones Z in the system. The superscript i represents the zone the units belong to, while $F_{f,t}^{i,j}$ represents the power flows in and out of each zone. The model can account for asymmetrical bi-directional flows, limited by the NTC or flow-based rating (Eq. 1l). The operating limits of the generating units are presented with the inequality constraints in Eqs. 1c - 1g, and Eq. 1l. The ramp rate constraints for thermal units are presented in Eqs. 1d - 1e. These constraints ensure that ramping up/down the power generated by the unit does not exceed its technical limitations. Here, we assume $P_s^{min} = 0$ for all storage units. The state of charge constraints are presented in Eqs. 1h - 1j, where $E_{s,t}$ is the current storage level, $SI_{s,t}$ is the self-discharge rate, $SI_{s,t}$ represent the hourly inflows and $SW_{s,t}$ are the waste outflows.

Eq. 1k mandates the storage level of each unit at the end of the time horizon to be at least equal to the level at the beginning of the optimization. This constraint motivates the cycling of units with charging capabilities, as well as ensuring a predictable water level at the beginning of the year for large hydro dam units. The difference between the charging ($\eta_{C,s}$) and discharging ($\eta_{D,s}$) efficiencies discourages the solver from utilizing these actions simultaneously. We use this approach to avoid utilizing binary variables that can severely prolong the computation time. Finally, Eq. 1m shows the inequality constraint that allows for demand shedding, where $D_{sch,t}$ is the scheduled demand of each consumer for the particular hour.

We observe that most of the constraints of the UC are similar to the ED constraints, with Eqs 2c - 2g representing the thermal unit constraints and Eqs 2h - 2l representing the storage unit constraints. Nevertheless, several notable differences exist. The costs for thermal units also include b_g^{on} and b_g^{off} that represent the startup and shutdown costs,

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respectively. These costs are incurred by the unit every time it switches its operating status, represented by the binary decision variables $\nu_{g,t}^{on}$ and $\nu_{g,t}^{off}$. The current operating status of the unit for every time increment in Eqs. 2c,f, and g is represented with the binary variable $\nu_{g,t}^{stat}$. By adding the binary variables, we transform the model into a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) problem. Compared to the ED, the UC model sacrifices computational efficiency for improved accuracy, addressing its most significant drawbacks.

exceeds the minimum up/down time and ramp limits of storage units.

II. UNIT COMMITMENT MODEL

The unit commitment model (UC) is formulated as a cost-minimization problem with the objective of minimizing the total costs in the system, subject to equality and inequality constraints (Eq. 2).

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{P_g, PD_s, PC_s, P_r, D_d} \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{g \in N_G} (P_{g,t} \cdot b_g + \nu_{g,t}^{on} \cdot b_g^{on} \\ & + \nu_{g,t}^{off} \cdot b_g^{off}) + \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{s \in N_S} (PD_{s,t} + PC_{s,t} + SW_{s,t}) \cdot b_s \\ & + \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{r \in N_R} P_{r,t} \cdot b_r + \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{d \in N_D} (D_{sch,t} - D_{d,t}) \cdot b_{ds} \quad (2a) \end{aligned}$$

s.t.

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\sum_{g \in N_G} P_{g,t}^i + \sum_{r \in N_R} P_{r,t}^i + \sum_{s \in N_S} PD_{s,t}^i - \sum_{s \in N_S} PC_{s,t}^i \right) \\ & - \sum_{d \in N_D} D_{d,t}^i + \sum_{\substack{f \in N_F \\ i \neq j}} F_{f,t}^{i,j} = 0, \quad \forall t, \forall i, j \in Z \quad (2b) \end{aligned}$$

$$P_g^{min} \cdot \nu_g^{stat} \leq P_{g,t} \leq P_g^{max} \cdot \nu_g^{stat}, \quad \forall \{g, t\} \quad (2c)$$

$$P_{g,t+1} - P_{g,t} \leq RU_g, \quad \forall \{g, t\} \quad (2d)$$

$$P_{g,t} - P_{g,t-1} \leq RD_g, \quad \forall \{g, t\} \quad (2e)$$

$$\nu_{g,t+1}^{stat} - \nu_{g,t}^{stat} = \nu_{g,t}^{on} - \nu_{g,t}^{off}, \quad \forall \{g, t\} \quad (2f)$$

$$\nu_{g,t}^{on} + \nu_{g,t}^{off} \leq 1, \quad \forall \{g, t\} \quad (2g)$$

$$PD_s^{min} \leq PD_{s,t} \leq PD_s^{max}, \quad \forall \{s, t\} \quad (2h)$$

$$PC_s^{min} \leq PC_{s,t} \leq PC_s^{max}, \quad \forall \{s, t\} \quad (2i)$$

$$E_s^{min} \leq E_{s,t} \leq E_s^{max}, \quad \forall \{s, t\} \quad (2j)$$

$$\begin{aligned} E_{s,t} = & (1 - SD_{rate}) \cdot E_{s,t-1} + \eta_{C,s} \cdot PC_{s,t} \\ & - 1/\eta_{D,s} \cdot PD_{s,t} + SI_{s,t} - SW_{s,t}, \quad \forall \{s, t\} \quad (2k) \end{aligned}$$

$$0 \leq SW_{s,t} \leq SW_s^{max}, \quad \forall \{s, t\} \quad (2l)$$

$$E_{s,t=T} \geq E_{s,t=0}, \quad \forall \{s, t\} \quad (2m)$$

$$0 \leq P_{r,t} \leq P_r^{max}, \quad \forall \{r, t\} \quad (2n)$$

$$0 \leq D_{d,t} \leq D_{sch,t}, \quad \forall \{d, t\} \quad (2o)$$

$$0 \leq F_{f,t} \leq F_f^{max}, \quad \forall \{f, t\} \quad (2p)$$

In Eq. 2c, where the technical limits can be set to zero by the status variable $\nu_{g,t}^{stat}$. Eq. 2f shows how the on and off constraints influence the status variable, while Eq. 2g prevents the simultaneous occurrence of on and off signals. In this model, only thermal units contain binary variables due to the fast operating nature of storage units. The lowest temporal resolution in the EuroEM framework is 1 hour, which usually